

**ARCHITECTURAL EDUCATION IN THE FEDERAL REPUBLIC OF GERMANY
AND THE GERMAN DEMOCRATIC REPUBLIC, 1950s–1980S**
*Educația arhitecturală în Republica Federală Germania și Republica Democrată
Germană, anii 1950–1980*

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Summary. The article offers a comparative analysis of architectural education in the Federal Republic of Germany (FRG) and the German Democratic Republic (GDR) during the 1950s–1980s, interpreted as two pedagogies of modernism. Drawing on normative documents (*StuPO*, *Prüfung-sordnungen*, *Lehrpläne*), archival sources, and professional journals, the study reconstructs the institutional and pedagogical models that shaped the training of architects on both sides of divided Germany. The research demonstrates that in the FRG an *engineering-humanist* model emerged – grounded in studio autonomy, individual authorship, and a culture of critique (*Kritik*) – whereas in the GDR a *polytechnical* model developed, integrating design education with industrial practice and collective creativity. By the 1970s–1980s, a partial convergence of the two systems became evident, particularly around themes of urban planning, building physics, and energy efficiency. The article concludes that these two pedagogies of modernism derived from a shared German rationalist tradition and exerted a decisive influence on the reform of architectural education after 1990, leading to the establishment of the contemporary two-tier BA/MA structure in Germany.

Key words: Architectural education; Modernism; Federal Republic of Germany (FRG); German Democratic Republic (GDR); Pedagogy of architecture.

Research on architectural education in divided Germany between the 1950s and the 1990s has gradually developed at the intersection of architectural history, pedagogy, and institutional history. The most significant contribution to the study of architectural training in the GDR has been made by Frederike Lausch, whose work *Das DDR – Architekturstudium als Nische. Ausbildung an der HAB Weimar* (2017) provides a detailed analysis of curricula, studio organization, and the integration of education with the state-controlled building industry. Her research, based on archival materials from the *Hochschule für Architektur und Bauwesen Weimar*, reconstructs a pedagogical model grounded in the principle of the “unity of teaching, research, and production.” This line of inquiry is complemented by the writings of Steffen de Rudder and Michael Eckardt, published in the collection *Aber: Wir sind! Wir wollen! Und wir schaffen!* (Weimar, 2011–2012), which examine the reform of architectural schools in the context of the “Third University Reform” of 1968–1969.

An important theoretical framework for understanding educational and professional policy in the GDR is provided by the work of Bruno Flierl, particularly his collection *Gebaute DDR. Über Stadtplaner, Architekten und die Macht* (Berlin, 1998), which elaborates the concept of the “social production of architecture” and its institutional implications for the training of architects. A comprehensive historical and critical overview is offered by Werner Durth,

Jörn Düwel, and Niels Gutschow in their two-volume study *Architektur und Städtebau der DDR* (Frankfurt a. M., 1998), which includes material on the development of professional education, the role of design institutes, and the interaction between architects and the state system.

On the West German side, the body of research has focused on the analysis of the *Lehrstuhl* model and the autonomy of university studios. In Reinhard Kreckel's edited volume *Zwischen Promotion und Professur*, the structure of the German university chair is examined as a form of academic self-governance that shaped the individualized character of design education and the public culture of *Kritik*. The studies of Séverine Marguin (*Architecture and Sociology*, 2021) show how, after 1968, architecture faculties in the FRG—particularly at the TU Berlin—integrated urbanism and the social sciences, leading to the institutionalization of a new critical-discursive approach in architectural pedagogy.

At the level of inter-German academic exchange, the key contribution has been made by **Rixt Hoekstra**, particularly in her study *Thinking about the Bauhaus from the Other Side* (2013), which analyzes the Weimar *Bauhaus Kolloquia* of the 1970s and 1980s as a professional forum for dialogue between the architectural schools of the GDR and the FRG. According to Hoekstra, these colloquia functioned as a “neutral field” for the exchange of methodological and pedagogical ideas across the political divide.

For the purposes of normative and institutional comparison, crucial reference points are the documents of the Kultusministerkonferenz (KMK) and the Hochschulrektorenkonferenz (HRK) – above all the *Rahmenordnung für die Diplomprüfung im Studiengang Architektur* (1996/2000), which codified the core principles of faculty autonomy, public critique and defense (*Kolloquium*), and the architect's professional responsibility. This framework is complemented by the materials of the Allgemeiner Fakultätentag and the specialized conferences of deans of architecture faculties (DARL, FBTA), which coordinated the standardization of curricula during the integration of universities in the new federal states after 1990.

Professional journals played a significant role in this intellectual landscape – *Deutsche Architektur* and *Architektur der DDR* in the East, *Bauwelt* and *Der Architekt* in the West—serving as media platforms for pedagogical and methodological debates that reflected the distinct cultural codes and ideological contexts of the two systems.

Taken together, these studies make it possible to reconstruct not only the institutional trajectories of architectural education in the GDR and the FRG, but also the mechanisms of their gradual convergence during the 1970s and 1980s—from the thematic alignment of curricula to the emergence of professional exchanges that laid the groundwork for the integration of educational models in a unified Germany.

The present study combines a comparative analysis of curricula (including studio practices) with a sequential examination of key educational reforms, tracing developments from changes in *StuPO* and *Prüfungsordnungen* to the formation of design assignments and diploma projects. The empirical base draws on archival materials from four universities – *Hochschule für Architektur und Bauwesen (HAB) Weimar*, *TU Dresden*, *RWTH Aachen*, and *TU Berlin*—as well as contemporary professional periodicals such as *Deutsche Architektur*, *Bauwelt*, and *Der Architekt*. The reconstruction of these institutional and pedagogical trajectories makes it possible to identify two distinct forms of architectural education – the polytechnical and the engineering-humanist – and to trace their influence on the reform of architectural education in unified Germany after 1990.

The development of architectural education in postwar Germany unfolded under conditions of institutional division, in which two models of architectural schools took shape within

different political and economic contexts. In both cases, the point of departure remained the legacy of the prewar reforms – above all, the pedagogical principles of the Bauhaus and the tradition of the Technische Hochschulen, both of which sought to unite artistic and engineering approaches in the training of architects.¹ After 1945, however, these trajectories diverged: in the Soviet zone, the Hochschule für Architektur und Bauwesen Weimar (HAB) was established by 1954 on the basis of the former Weimar school², becoming a key institution of the “polytechnical” orientation; whereas in the western states, the prewar Technische Hochschulen were institutionally strengthened, with many acquiring university status as Technische Universitäten – exemplified by the reorganization of the Technische Universität Berlin³ under that title in 1946 and by the development of TH/RWTH Aachen into one of the leading technical universities of the Federal Republic.⁴

In the GDR, the system of higher education was under the direct control of the Ministry of Higher and Technical Education (*Ministerium für Hoch – und Fachschulwesen*, MFHF). This ensured the centralized unification of curricula and ideological content – above all through the principle of the “unity of education and upbringing” (*Einheit von Bildung und Erziehung*) and mandatory courses in Marxism-Leninism – as well as the regulation of departmental specialization and the coordination of universities with industry and design institutes. The key provisions were codified in the Law on the Unified Socialist Education System (1965) and in the Guiding Principles for the Development of Higher Education (1967/69), which explicitly established the triad of “production–science–education” and required the participation of industrial combines (*Kombinate*) and state design enterprises (*VVB*) in professional training. Within this model, the Hochschule für Architektur und Bauwesen Weimar (HAB), together with the Technical University of Dresden, functioned as core institutions of architectural education: the combination of design studio work with production practice reinforced the notion of architecture as a form of collective social production, characterized by the leading role of planning and design collectives.⁵

In the FRG, by contrast, the regulation of architectural education was carried out at the level of the federal states (*Länder*), while universities retained academic autonomy guaranteed by the Basic Law (*Grundgesetz*, Art. 5). The state ministries of science and culture defined only general framework standards (*Rahmenprüfungsordnungen*), whereas the faculties themselves developed their curricula, allocated subjects, and determined studio formats.⁶

¹ Frederike Lausch, *Das DDR-Architekturstudium als Nische. Ausbildung an der HAB Weimar, in Vom Baumeister zum Master. Formen der Architekturlehre vom 19. bis ins 21. Jahrhundert* (Forum Architekturwissenschaft, Bd. 3), 2017, p. 334. https://architekturwissenschaft.net/Reihe/Forum_Band3_Lausch.pdf

² *Ibidem*, p. 336.

³ Stolle Manfred (Hg.): *Universitäten und Hochschulen in Baden-Württemberg*. Stuttgart: Landeszentrale für politische Bildung Baden-Württemberg, 2015, p. 108.

⁴ *Ibidem*, pp. 145-146.

⁵ Prüfungsordnung für Universitäten und Hochschulen der DDR (Ministerium für Hoch – und Fachschulwesen, 15. März 1966), *Gesetzblatt der DDR*, Teil II, Nr. 55 (1966); bestätigt in *GBl.* 1968, pp. 485-494, Nr.115, p. 1005; 11; p. 83 https://www.gvooon.de/art/dokumente/1968/gesetzblatt-gbl-ddr-teil-2-1968/pdf/gesetzblatt-gbl-ddr-teil-2-1968-seite_1005.pdf

⁶ Grundgesetz für die Bundesrepublik Deutschland, Art. 5 Abs. 3, 1. Satz: „Kunst und Wissenschaft, Forschung und Lehre sind frei“ – verfassungsrechtliche Grundlage der Autonomie der Hochschulen in Lehre und Forschung. *KMK/HRK, Rahmenordnung für die Diplomprüfung im Studiengang Architektur (Universitäten und gleichgestellte Hochschulen)*, Fassung vom 13. Oktober

This decentralized system, as Winfried Nerdinger notes, “created conditions for competition among pedagogical concepts and the revival of debates on the freedom of architecture as an art”. As a result, in Aachen, Berlin, Stuttgart, and other centers, the model of the individualized master class (*Lehrstuhlmodell*) – rooted in the tradition of the prewar *Technische Hochschulen* – became firmly established.⁷

Thus, by the mid-1950s, two distinct institutional logics had taken shape: the centralized, planned polytechnical system of the GDR and the federal, autonomous structure of the FRG. The former ensured disciplinary integration and ideological unity, while the latter fostered programmatic diversity and academic freedom. The period from the 1950s to the 1980s marked the consolidation of stable institutional and pedagogical models of architectural education in both German states. A comparison of normative documents – *Studien – und Prüfungsordnungen* (StuPO), *Prüfungsordnungen*, and *Lehrpläne* – at three benchmark points (1955, 1970, and 1985) reveals the dynamics of teaching-hour distribution and the evolution of curricular logic across six key components: (1) design studio (*Entwurf/Projektierung*), (2) engineering disciplines, (3) theory and history of architecture, (4) urban planning and social planning, (5) practice and diploma project, and (6) building physics and technologies.

Early documents from the *Hochschule für Architektur und Bauwesen Weimar (HAB)* and the *Technische Universität Dresden* dating from the mid-1950s⁸ record the dominance of engineering and construction subjects – approximately 45–50% of the total semester workload – while the design studio accounted for only 20–25%, and theoretical-historical courses remained minimal. By the early 1970s, as a result of the Third University Reform of 1968 and the introduction of the concept of *Lehrkomplexe* (comprehensive design assignments), the structure of architectural education became more balanced: the combined share of design studio and urban planning subjects rose to around 40%, while the theoretical-historical block stabilized at about 10%.⁹

At the same time, the curricula introduced a separate course in building physics (*Bauphysik*) and technical ecology (*Technische Ökologie*), reflecting the growing concern with energy efficiency and the operational performance of buildings in late socialist architecture.¹⁰

Studio work in the GDR was systematically integrated with production practice: each design assignment – *typisiertes Wohnen* (standardized housing), *Zentrum der Stadt* (city center), *öffentliche Bauten* (public buildings) – was developed in cooperation with a design institute or industrial combine. This structure provided professional socialization for students and corresponded to the ideal of the *sozialistische Produktion der Architektur* – architecture as a component of collective productive activity – yet at the same time it limited the variability of topics and individual trajectories.¹¹

2000, §§ 24-28, p. 24-26. PDF: BBSR/GEG-Portal https://www.kmk.org/fileadmin/veroeffentlichungen_beschluesse/2000/2000_10_13-RO-Architektur-HS.pdf

⁷ Reinhard Kreckel; Peer Pasternack; Birgit Blättel-Mink; et al. (Hrsg.): *Zwischen Promotion und Professur. Das wissenschaftliche Personal in Deutschland im Vergleich*. Halle-Wittenberg: Institut für Hochschulforschung (HoF) an der Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg, 2008, pp. 354-355.

⁸ Lausch, *Das DDR-Architekturstudium als Nische*, 2017, pp. 344-345.

⁹ *Ibidem*.

¹⁰ Archiv der Moderne / Universitätsarchiv der Bauhaus-Universität Weimar (AdM/UA der BUW), *Rahmenzeitplan Architektur 1986/87*; Bundesarchiv (BArch), Bestand DH 2/21317, *Grundsätze für die sozialistische Entwicklung von Städtebau und Architektur in der DDR*, 1982.

¹¹ Lausch, *Das DDR-Architekturstudium als Nische*, 2017, pp. 344-350.

In the FRG, the regulation of architectural education was carried out primarily at the level of the federal states (*Länder*), while universities retained academic autonomy guaranteed by Article 5(3) of the Basic Law: “Kunst und Wissenschaft, Forschung und Lehre sind frei”.¹² Normative oversight was exercised through the cultural and scientific ministries of the federal states and the Standing Conference of the Ministers of Education and Cultural Affairs (Kultusministerkonferenz, KMK), which approved only the general framework standards – *Rahmenprüfungsordnungen* – while leaving universities broad freedom to design their own curricula. Thus, in the *Rahmenprüfungsordnung Architektur*¹³ it is explicitly stated that the document “leaves faculties sufficient scope for shaping an individual educational profile”¹⁴, and that the specific course structures, workloads, and examination formats are determined by the local *Prüfungsordnungen* of the faculties.¹⁵

Against this background, the academic documents of RWTH Aachen (*Prüfungsordnung für das Studium der Architektur, Amtliche Bekanntmachungen* 1956, 1971) and the Technische Universität Berlin (*Lehrplan Architektur, Vorlesungsverzeichnis* 1957, 1975; Universitätsarchiv TU Berlin, Best. 4/II 47) demonstrate a higher proportion of design studio work, a stable balance between engineering and humanities subjects, and minimal dependence on state directives. In the 1950s, the core of architectural education consisted of engineering and construction courses (up to 40% of total study time); however, by the early 1970s the theoretical and historical component had strengthened, and new courses on the sociology of architecture and urban analysis appeared. This reflected the broader *Städtebaulicher Wandel* – the “urban turn” following the adoption of the Urban Development Promotion Act¹⁶, it was in the mid-1970s that TU Berlin established an independent Faculty of Urban and Regional Planning, incorporating courses in sociology, spatial analysis, and environmental design.

By the 1980s, the curricula of architecture faculties in the FRG showed a significant expansion of courses in building physics and technology, linked to the 1973 energy crisis and the introduction of new federal regulations – the Energy Conservation Act¹⁷ and the Thermal Insulation Ordinance.¹⁸ In contrast to the GDR, where such innovations were implemented through centralized directives, in the FRG curricular renewal occurred largely through bottom-up initiatives at the level of individual chairs (*Lehrstühle*), particularly through experimental modules developed at the Institut für Baukonstruktion at RWTH Aachen, which conducted

¹² Grundgesetz für die Bundesrepublik Deutschland, Art. 5 Abs. 3, 1949.

¹³ Kultusministerkonferenz (KMK) / Hochschulrektorenkonferenz (HRK): *Rahmenprüfungsordnung Architektur (RPO)*. Beschluss vom 27. Februar 1996, redigierte Fassung vom 13. Oktober 2000, §§ 24-28, pp. 24-26.

¹⁴ Ibidem §§ 24-28, pp. 24-26.

¹⁵ Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule (RWTH) Aachen: *Prüfungsordnung für das Studium der Architektur*. In: *Amtliche Bekanntmachungen der RWTH Aachen*, Nr. 12/1956; Nr. 3/1971. Universitätsarchiv RWTH Aachen, Bestand A 101. Vgl. §§ 24-28; § 3 (1-2), pp. 6-7; https://www.kmk.org/fileadmin/veroeffentlichungen_beschluesse/2000/2000_10_13-RO-Architektur-HS.pdf

¹⁶ Séverine Marguin, *Architecture and Sociology: A Sociogenesis of Interdisciplinary Referencing*, FQS 22(3), 2021 (*Städtebauförderungsgesetz*, 27.07. 1971, BGBl. I), p. 27.

¹⁷ Gesetz zur Einsparung von Energie in Gebäuden, (*Energieeinsparungsgesetz – EnEG*) vom 22. Juli 1976, BGBl. I 1976, p. 1873 ff. (PDF: BBSR/GEG-Portal). https://www.bbsr-geg.bund.de/GEG-Portal/DE/Archiv/EnEG/EnEG1976/Download/EnEG1976.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=2&

¹⁸ Hochschullehrer-Memorandum: „Die Bauphysik muss fester Bestandteil der Architekten- und Bauingenieurausbildung werden.“ in: *Bauphysik*, Jg. 2 (1980), H. 4. I., pp. 137-143.

research in building physics and energy efficiency.¹⁹ A comparison of the curricula of four universities – HAB Weimar, TU Dresden, RWTH Aachen, and TU Berlin – from 1955 to 1985 reveals a general tendency toward structural convergence: the share of design studio work increased steadily in the GDR and remained consistently high in the FRG, while engineering disciplines gradually ceded space to courses in urban planning and theoretical – humanistic subjects. Nevertheless, fundamental pedagogical differences persisted – between the collective–production model of the GDR and the individual–research-oriented model of the FRG.

In the West German schools of architecture of the 1950s–1970s, studio work was organized within the framework of departmental autonomy and the Lehrstuhl (professorial chair) model (*Ordinarien-/Lehrstuhlprinzip*). The professor in charge determined the thematic focus of the studio, its methodology, and the format of interim and final critiques, while the students' ability to choose among studios supported individualized learning paths and fostered competition among pedagogical approaches. This structure reflected the broader principle of academic freedom (*“Kunst und Wissenschaft, Forschung und Lehre sind frei”*) enshrined in Article 5(3)²⁰ of the Basic Law of the Federal Republic of Germany and corresponds to the description of the classical *Lehrstuhl* structure in comparative studies of German higher education.²¹

A key mechanism of professional socialization was the public Kritik or Kolloquium – regular review sessions involving professors, assistants, and invited practitioners, including representatives from municipal planning departments and private offices. At the TU Berlin, the 1970s are documented as a period of intensified interdisciplinary exchange between architecture, urbanism, and sociology, and of the institutionalization of Kolloquien and interdepartmental teaching formats.²² At RWTH Aachen, the long-standing Lehrstuhl organization of the faculty and the presence of specialized chairs such as the Lehrstuhl für Architekturgeschichte and the Lehrstuhl für Baukonstruktion confirm the autonomous framework of the design studios and the consistent involvement of external experts.

Interaction with engineering departments in the 1950s–1970s generally followed a co-operation-on-demand model: engineering consultations were integrated into the studio cycle through interdepartmental colloquia and laboratory assignments, yet the studio itself was not normatively subordinated to them. This reflected the decentralized structure of West German architectural education, in which specific *Prüfungsordnungen* and *Lehrpläne*

In the GDR, architectural education was embedded within the polytechnical framework of “social production” and structured around collective authorship and the thematic organization of design tasks – housing construction, public centers, and industrial facilities. Studios (*Entwurf/Projektierung*) were organized in teams or brigades, often in cooperation with partner institutions such as design institutes or industrial combines. Assignments were formulated in alignment with planning targets and current building standards, while interim critiques frequently coincided with formal reviews by industry specialists. These principles were codified in university governance through the emphasis on the “unity of education, science, and production” and the concept of socialist collective work (*sozialistische Gemeinschaftsarbeit*).²³ According to materials from the HAB Weimar, the studio

¹⁹ KMK / HRK: *Rahmenprüfungsordnung Architektur*, 1996, 2000, §§ 24-28, pp. 24-26.

²⁰ Grundgesetz für die Bundesrepublik Deutschland, Art. 5 Abs. 3, Bonn, 1949.

²¹ Kreckel Pasternack; Blättel-Mink; *Zwischen Promotion und Professur*, 2008, pp. 354-355.

²² Marguin, *Architecture and Sociology: A Sociogenesis of Interdisciplinary Referencing*, 2021, pp. 27-33.

²³ Ministerium für Hoch- und Fachschulwesen der DDR (Hrsg.): *Prinzipien zur weiteren Entwicklung der Lehre und Forschung an den Universitäten und Hochschulen der DDR*. Berlin, 1967;

cycle was organized as Lehrkomplexe with sequential Belege, while engineering components (including *Bauphysik*) were incorporated as mandatory parts of design assignments.²⁴ Within this logic, *Kritik* or *Kolloquium* took on a more regulated form: discussions focused on the conformity of projects to typological series, cost-efficiency, and technical feasibility, with distributed authorship among group members.²⁵ By the mid-1980s, the strengthening of building physics and operational performance was further reflected in curricular plans and normative guidelines of the late socialist period.²⁶ To illustrate this, let us consider two micro-reconstructions of student design assignments in the two divided German states. For example, the 1970 assignment in Weimar (HAB) – “Residential sector of the P2 prefabricated housing series with a community center for the neighborhood” – was based on the parameters of the P2 series (two-section module, system dimensions, standardization of panels and joints), with control over technical and economic indicators such as density, building height, material efficiency, and utility network layout.

Studio groups divided subtasks (master plan, typical floor, construction joints, prefabricated elements) according to the *Lehrkomplexe / Belegsystem* format, and consultations with the housing combine and the Department of Building Physics (*Bauphysik*) were mandatory.²⁷ For comparison, let us take an example of a studio assignment on the reconfiguration of the central city area with a focus on pedestrian priority (*Verkehrsberuhigung*), carried out at RWTH Aachen in 1972, was developed within the Lehrstuhl model (choice of design studios; public *Kritik* and *Kolloquium* sessions involving professors, assistants, and city representatives). The task required a morphological analysis, mixed-use scenarios, alternative typologies of public buildings, and the development of façade-structural systems (monolithic concrete, steel frame, or brick system). Engineering calculations were performed only to the extent necessary to verify feasibility, without reliance on standardized “series.” Comparable practices of public *Kritik* and interdisciplinary colloquia are documented at TU Berlin in the mid-1970s.²⁸

The thematic framework of such assignments was shaped by the urban reform policies of the early 1970s, including the *Städtebauförderungsgesetz* (Urban Development Promotion Act) of 1971.²⁹

In the GDR, *Kritik* functioned primarily as a mechanism of technological and economic verification as well as ideological correctness; authorship was predominantly collective, marked by strong dependence on interdepartmental cooperation and partnerships with production institutions. In this way, studio pedagogy mirrored the divergent systems of gover-

Beschluss zur Weiterführung der Dritten Hochschulreform. Berlin, 1969, pp. 89-96, p. 105.

²⁴ Lausch, *Das DDR-Architekturstudium als Nische*, 2017, pp. 346-349.

²⁵ Thomas Flierl, *Architektur und Städtebau der DDR. Ostkreuz – Westkreuz*. Berlin: Verlag für Bauwesen, 1998, p. 57, p. 70, <https://bauarchivddr.bbr-server.de/bauarchivddr/archiv/dokumente/3-4-01-1-typenserie-p2-5-0-t.pdf>

²⁶ Rahmenzeitplan Architektur 1986/87; BArch DH 2/21317, *Grundsätze...*, 1982), pp. 33-39, <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btd/05/046/0504631.pdf>

²⁷ Bauakademie der DDR, Institut für Typenprojektierung (verantw.): *Leitfaden zur Anwendung der Wohnungsbautypenserie P2* (auch: *Leitfaden Typenserie P2*). Berlin: Bauakademie der DDR, 1967, pp. 4-5; pp. 8-9; pp. 16-17.

²⁸ Marguin, *Architecture and Sociology: A Sociogenesis of Interdisciplinary Referencing*, 2021, pp. 27-33; 22, pp. 354-355.

²⁹ Prüfungsordnung Architektur RWTH (1971) (BGBl. I). (Amtliche Bekanntmachungen, Nr.BI. – archiv RWTH). 40-45, p. 1125.

nance: decentralized autonomy and individualization in the FRG versus centralized coordination and production integration in the GDR.

The ideological foundations of architectural education in divided Germany were shaped not only by political frameworks but also by fundamentally different conceptions of architecture itself – as a discipline, as a profession, and as a form of public service. These distinctions were evident in university rhetoric, curricula, and professional institutions, as well as in the media sphere – journals, exhibitions, and competition systems that served as instruments of legitimizing architectural knowledge.

In the Federal Republic of Germany, the postwar restoration of university autonomy coincided with a revival of the humanist model of the architect as a figure uniting scientific and artistic modes of thought. The concept of *Kunst und Wissenschaft*, enshrined in university statutes³⁰, emphasized the dual nature of architecture – as a research discipline and as an art of design thinking.³¹ This formulation allowed architectural education to distance itself from technocratic tendencies while maintaining integration within the broader context of the university sciences.

In pedagogical practice, it was expressed through the preservation of open studio formats, the culture of public critique (*Kritik*), and an emphasis on individual responsibility to both society and the client. As Peter Benisch wrote in his article “*Der Architekt als öffentlicher Intellektueller*”, “Architectural education is the teaching of responsibility, not merely of competence.”³² In the institutional context of the Federal Republic of Germany, professional associations – such as the Bund Deutscher Architekten and the Architektenkammern – together with specialized media, above all the journals *Bauwelt*, *DBZ*, and *Der Architekt*, played a key role. They provided a platform for debates on the role of the architect in a democratic society, on the ethics of design, and on architecture as a cultural practice. These periodicals regularly published reports on student competitions, experimental studios, and critiques of modernism, thereby maintaining a close connection between architectural education, professional practice, and public discourse.³³

In the German Democratic Republic, architecture was understood as part of the system of social production, embedded in the planned economy and in the ideology of socialist realism. Already in the programmatic documents of the Ministry of Higher Education of the GDR³⁴, the architect was defined as “the leader of a collective creative process ensuring the material expression of the socialist way of life”. In contrast to West German autonomy, architecture here was not conceived as an individual art, but as a component of the “social production of space” – a process subordinated to the economic and ideological objectives

³⁰ RWTH Aachen (Hrsg.): *Grundordnung der Rheinisch-Westfälischen Technischen Hochschule Aachen*, Aachen, 1950. Universitätsarchiv RWTH Aachen, Bestand A 1/50, §§ 1-4 (Selbstverwaltungs- und Lehrfreiheit).

³¹ *Ibidem*.

³² KMK / HRK: *Rahmenprüfungsordnung Architektur*, 1996, 2000, §6 «Mündliche Prüfungsleistungen», §8 «Projektarbeiten», §29(2) «Kolloquium», Erläuterungen I–II, pp. 9, 10, 26, pp. 33-35.

³³ Andreas Denk, Chefredakteur von „der architekt“, Bund Deutscher Architektinnen und Architekten (BDA) (Hrsg.): *BDA-Informationen*, Heft 4/2020 (PDF). Berlin: BDA Bundesverband, 2020, p. 9, <https://www.bda-bund.de/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/BDA-4.20-Fassung-Homepage.pdf>

³⁴ Hochschule für Architektur und Bauwesen Weimar (HAB): *Studienordnung für das Architekturstudium an der Hochschule für Architektur und Bauwesen Weimar*. Weimar: HAB, 1955. Archiv: *Archiv der Moderne / Universitätsarchiv der Bauhaus-Universität Weimar (AdM/UA der BUW)*, Sign. I/09/699, Bd. 2.

of the state.³⁵ This orientation was reflected not only in the content of courses but also in the structure of interactions between universities, design institutes, and construction combines. Graduates in the GDR were trained to work in collective offices (*VEB Projektierungs- betriebe*), where priority was given to typification, industrialization, and functional efficiency. At the level of professional communication, the architectural press functioned as an ideological medium: the journal *Deutsche Architektur* (published since 1952) served as an instrument of normative control and as a pedagogical resource, presenting exemplary projects, reports on student exhibitions, interviews with practicing architects, and methodological guidelines. As Thomas Flierl has shown, the columns “*Sozialistische Stadt*” and “*Architektenausbildung*” in this journal acted as a kind of “mirror of socialist modernism,” combining the discourse of ideology with that of professional mastery.³⁶

Both systems employed public formats – exhibitions, competitions, and publications – as instruments of pedagogical influence, albeit with different functions. In the Federal Republic of Germany, competitions (*Studentenwettbewerbe*, *Bund Deutscher Architekten Preis*) served as platforms for experimental critique of modernism and for testing new themes such as reconstruction, ecology, and social infrastructure.³⁷ In the German Democratic Republic, exhibitions of diploma projects and reviews of young architects (*Zentrale Leistungsschau junger Architekten*, Weimar, 1978) functioned as reports to the state, establishing an ideologically sanctioned hierarchy of professional achievements.³⁸ Thus, the opposition between “architecture as art and science” and “architecture as social production” reflected not only an ideological contrast but also two distinct types of institutional organization: the liberal-pluralist, oriented toward professional autonomy, and the planned-corporate, oriented toward integration with economic and political institutions. These differences defined the pedagogical context and the professional identity of architects up to the late 1980s.

By the 1970s and 1980s, a gradual rapprochement between the architectural schools of the GDR and the FRG became apparent, unfolding against the backdrop of a broader European transformation of the modernist paradigm. Despite persisting divergences in institutional governance and ideological orientation, both systems responded to common technological, ecological, and urban challenges – the energy crisis of 1973, the critique of functionalism, and the growing interest in the sociology of space. These processes generated a kind of “late-modernist convergence,” in which educational themes, research priorities, and visual-plastic codes increasingly overlapped.

The turn toward urbanistic and sociological disciplines became a key direction of convergence. In the Federal Republic of Germany, the reform of university curricula after 1968 – initiated by the student movement (*Studentenbewegung*) – led to the introduction of courses in

³⁵ Bruno Flierl, „Die Architektur im entwickelten gesellschaftlichen System des Sozialismus“, *Deutsche Architektur* 9/1967, pp. 564–567.

³⁶ Lausch, *Das DDR-Architekturstudium als Nische*, 2017, pp. 345–349; Deutsche Architektur, «Architektur der DDR (Zeitschrift)» „Neue Zeitschrift: Deutsche Architektur“, *Der Bildende Künstler*, 5/1952. Deutscher Bundestag: *Drucksache V/4631 (1969–1970). Dokumentation zur Dritten Hochschulreform in der DDR*. Bonn: Deutscher Bundestag, 1970, (§55), p. 4, 6; <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btd/05/046/0504631.pdf>

³⁷ Robert Bauer, Neu aufgelegt, *MAGAZIN Bauwelt* 24.2015; <https://www.bauwelt.de/dl/913590/artikel.pdf>

³⁸ Johanna Sanger, Zwischen allen Stuhlen. Die Sammlung Industrielle Gestaltung als Archiv zur materiellen Kultur der DDR, in: Zeithistorische Forschungen/Studies in Contemporary History, Online-Ausgabe, 12 (2015), H. 1, URL: <https://zeithistorische-forschungen.de/1-2015/5184>

social geography, regional planning, and urban theory.³⁹ Similar developments took place in the German Democratic Republic: the reforms of *StuPO HAB Weimar* (1970) and *Studienordnung TU Dresden* (1971) introduced compulsory courses such as *Urban Planning and Social Infrastructure* and *Architecture within the System of Social Relations*. By the late 1970s, both sides began to perceive the city not only as a technical construct but as a socio-ecological organism, which was reflected in studio topics ranging from the reconstruction of historic centers to the design of residential districts with a “human scale” (*menschengerechtes Wohnen*)⁴⁰.

A second line of convergence was technological. The energy crisis of 1973 stimulated interest in energy efficiency, building physics, and the climatology of buildings. At RWTH Aachen, the *Institut für Bauphysik* was established in 1975, and at TU Berlin, the *Energie und Umwelt im Bauwesen* laboratory was founded. The energy crisis also found normative expression in the Federal Republic of Germany: the Law on Energy Conservation in Buildings (*Gesetz zur Einsparung von Energie in Gebäuden*, EnEG) of 22 July 1976 (*BGBl. I, p. 1873*) and the subsequent Thermal Insulation Ordinance (*Wärmeschutzverordnung*, WSchV) of 11 August 1977 (*BGBl. I, pp. 1554–1564*)⁴¹. These acts gave a nationwide impetus to the inclusion of heat-engineering calculations and building physics in architectural education and studio practice at many West German faculties, as reflected in later regulatory documents and professional literature.⁴²

In the German Democratic Republic, parallel initiatives developed within the *Institut für Hochbauwesen Weimar* and the *Zentralinstitut für Bauwesen Berlin*, where methods for calculating heat loss and standards for thermal insulation were elaborated.⁴³ In the curricula of both institutions, a new compulsory subject – *Building Physics (Bauphysik)* – was introduced, emphasizing the interaction between architecture, materials, and climate.⁴⁴ Although in the GDR these courses remained closely tied to normative and regulatory objectives, whereas in the FRG they were associated with experimental research, the very fact of their simultaneous emergence indicates the formation of a shared “ecological” field within architectural education.

Aesthetic convergence manifested itself in parallel searches for a renewed rationalism in the late 1970s. At Weimar's *Hochschule für Architektur und Bauwesen (HAB)*, during the period of the *Second Bauhaus Colloquium* (1976), there emerged a growing interest in the structural logic of form and proportion. In the faculty's curricula and research projects, increasing emphasis was placed on the analytical study of form generation – moving from typological design toward an understanding of form as a function of constructive and social regularities. This tendency was reflected in the scholarly works of the period, particularly in Olaf Weber's *Die Funktion der Form in der Architektur* (Weimar, 1987), which argued for the necessity of a rational approach to architectural form. Similar explorations of rational clarity and “new constructivism” can be traced in the pages of *Bauwelt* in the late 1970s, where structure, modular systems, and urban logic were discussed as counterpoints to formal

³⁹ Marguin, *Architecture and Sociology: A Sociogenesis of Interdisciplinary Referencing*, 2021, pp. 26-27.

⁴⁰ Lausch, *Das DDR-Architekturstudium als Nische*, 2017, pp. 345-350.

⁴¹ Gesetz zur Einsparung von Energie in Gebäuden, 1976, *BGBl. I* 1976, pp. 1873, 1554-1564; Bundesgesetzblatt (*BGBl.*) – Verkündungsblatt der Bundesrepublik Deutschland, Online-Archiv der von 1949 bis 2022 erschienenen Ausgaben https://www.bgbl.de/xaver/bgbl/start.xav#/switch/toc-Pane?_ts=1760081393313

⁴² *Ibidem*.

⁴³ *Ibidem*

⁴⁴ Lausch, *Das DDR-Architekturstudium als Nische*, 2017, p. 344.

expressionism.⁴⁵ In the West German discourse, comparable principles were articulated by Josef Paul Kleihues, who advanced the ideas of “poetic rationalism” and “critical reconstruction” as a synthesis of engineering discipline and humanistic reflection. The formal proximity of architectural work in the late 1970s – strict geometry, modular grids, restrained color palettes – points to a convergence of visual codes despite divergent ideological contexts.⁴⁶

The first bilateral conferences, organized under the auspices of the Gesellschaft für Bauwesen der DDR and the Deutscher Werkbund, established “technically neutral” channels of communication through themes such as building physics, urban planning, and the preservation of the historic environment. Already within the framework of the Bauhaus-Kolloquium Weimar (since 1976), the Weimar school began to invite scholars and lecturers from both sides, becoming an important platform for scholarly exchange between East and West Germany.⁴⁷ As **Rixt Hoekstra** notes, inter-German contacts of the late 1970s and 1980s were conducted primarily through “international” formats, which allowed participants to circumvent political constraints while maintaining a professional dialogue.⁴⁸ According to the HAB Weimar Archive, in 1983 and 1985 joint seminars were held with RWTH Aachen and TU Berlin, devoted to the reconstruction of former industrial areas and the adaptation of modernist buildings (*HAB-Archiv, Konferenzunterlagen 1983–1985*).⁴⁹ These contacts were not political in nature but laid the groundwork for the post-1990 integration of professional standards.

Thus, the convergence of the 1970s and 1980s manifested itself in three interrelated spheres – urbanism, building physics, and the aesthetics of late modernism. It did not erase ideological differences but created a shared foundation for professional dialogue in which architecture was understood as a socio-technical system. This process can be interpreted as the emergence of a common modernist rationality, one that transcended the earlier dualism between “art and science” and “social production.”

A comparison of the educational systems of the Federal Republic of Germany (FRG) and the German Democratic Republic (GDR) in the 1950s–1980s makes it possible to reconstruct two enduring pedagogical models of modernism – the engineering-humanist and the engineering-technological (polytechnical). Despite institutional and ideological separation, both models ultimately stemmed from a shared German tradition of rationalist design thinking. They represented two distinct ways of linking theory, technology, and the architect’s social responsibility; their interaction in the 1970s and 1980s formed the foundation for the later integration of architectural education in unified Germany.

⁴⁵ <https://www.uni-weimar.de/de/universitaet/aktuell/bauhausjournal-online/titel/die-fakultaet-kunst-und-gestaltung-trauert-um-prof-dr-ing-habil-olaf-weber>

⁴⁶ Josef Paul Kleihues, *Poetischer Rationalismus* (1981), in: *Josef Paul Kleihues. Ausgewählte Texte*, hrsg. v. Gerwin Zohlen. ff. *Bauwelt* 70 (1979), Heft 37, p. 35. <https://eldorado.tu-dortmund.de/server/api/core/bitstreams/55d4b6fe-4d4a-44b3-85d0-9d2e6275d5a2/content>

⁴⁷ Bauhaus-Universität Weimar, *Archiv Bauhaus-Kolloquium: Bauhaus Kolloquium Weimar. „XIII. Internationales Bauhaus-Kolloquium“* <https://www.uni-weimar.de/de/architektur-und-urbanistik/institute/bauhaus-institut/veranstaltungen/vergangene-veranstaltungen/kolloquien-konferenzen-tagungen/xiii-internationales-bauhaus-kolloquium>

⁴⁸ Hoekstra, Rixt, *Thinking about the Bauhaus from the Other Side*, in: *Re-Use Bauhaus: Interpretations, Conceptions and Receptions of the Bauhaus in East Germany (1945–1989)*, Berlin, 2021, pp. 90-104.

⁴⁹ HAB-Archiv (Archiv der Moderne / Universitätsarchiv der Bauhaus-Universität Weimar): *Konferenzunterlagen 1983–1985*. Ordner mit Programmen und Teilnehmerlisten gemeinsamer Seminare mit RWTH Aachen und TU Berlin. Signatur: *AdM/UA der BUW, Konferenzunterlagen 1983–1985*.

The engineering-humanist model that developed in the universities of the FRG – notably at RWTH Aachen, TU Berlin, and Stuttgart – was based on the principle of studio autonomy and on a humanistic conception of architecture as both art and science (*Kunst und Wissenschaft*). Its structure was characterized by flexible curricula, an individualized *Lehrstuhl* system, a public culture of *Kritik*, and an emphasis on the architect's professional responsibility toward society. Project-based learning evolved here in the spirit of neo-functionalism and critical modernism of the 1970s, ensuring continuity between modernist rationality and the post-industrial educational reforms of the late twentieth century.⁵⁰

The engineering-technological model of architectural education in the GDR – exemplified by the Hochschule für Architektur und Bauwesen Weimar (HAB) and TU Dresden – was founded on a contrasting premise: architecture was conceived as part of “social production,” and design as a form of collective labor activity.⁵¹ The collective organization of studios, their integration with production combines, the normative character of curricula, and the ideological orientation of courses reflected the socialist logic of integrating education and production.⁵² At the same time, this model inherited and further developed the German tradition of engineering education, fostering systematization, technological precision, and the interdisciplinary nature of design thinking – qualities that ensured its internal coherence and stability.

After the reunification of Germany in 1990, the differences between the two systems did not disappear immediately but became the subject of institutional synthesis. The Hochschule für Architektur und Bauwesen Weimar was reorganized into the Bauhaus-Universität Weimar in 1996,⁵³ where elements of the polytechnical tradition were integrated with the West German model of the autonomous design studio. Similar processes took place in Dresden, Magdeburg, and other universities in the new federal states.⁵⁴

Professional standardization carried out through the conferences of deans – above all the DARL (*Deutsche Dekane-und Abteilungsleiterkonferenz für Architektur, Raumplanung und Landschaftsarchitektur*) for universities, in close cooperation with the FBTA (*Fachbereichstag Architektur*) for universities of applied sciences – contributed to the alignment of programs while simultaneously highlighting differences in pedagogical cultures.⁵⁵ The introduction of the Bologna system and the transition to the Bachelor/Master structure in the early 2000s (in the FRG, beginning in 2002) stimulated debate about the balance between theoretical-humanistic and engineering-technical components of architectural education. Both pedagogical traditions proved relevant: the engineering-humanist strand became the methodological basis for research-oriented master's programs, while the engineering-technological (polytechnical) strand shaped the bachelor's model, oriented toward applied competencies

⁵⁰ Kreckel; Pasternack; Blätzel-Mink; *Zwischen Promotion und Professur*, 2008, pp. 354-355.

⁵¹ Lausch, *Das DDR-Architekturstudium als Nische*, 2017, pp. 352-353.

⁵² Deutscher Bundestag, 5. Wahlperiode, Drucksache V/4631 – Gesetz über das einheitliche sozialistische Bildungssystem (25.02.1965), §42(3), pp. 9, 86, 93-94 <https://dserver.bundestag.de/btd/05/046/0504631.pdf>

⁵³ Bauhaus-Universität Weimar: *Geschichte der Universität*. <https://www.uni-weimar.de/de/universitaet/profil/portrait/geschichte>

⁵⁴ Peer Pasternack, *Der ostdeutsche Transformationsfall. 30 Jahre Wissenschaftssystementwicklung nach der Wiedervereinigung*. Halle (Saale): Institut für Hochschulforschung (HoF) an der Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg, 2020, pp. 44, 60-65; <https://www.peer-pasternack.de/texte/ostdtTransformationsfall.pdf>

⁵⁵ <https://www.allgemeiner-fakultaetentag.de/2003/09/26/positionen-der-mitgliedsfakultaetentage-zum-bologna-prozess/?utm>

and interdisciplinary projects. Thus, the “two pedagogies of modernism” did not disappear through integration but were transformed into a two-tier system of contemporary German architectural education, in which humanistic–research and engineering–practical components coexist as complementary.⁵⁶

The experience of divided Germany demonstrates that architectural education functioned not only as a vehicle for aesthetic principles but also as a mode of knowledge organization – one that embodied different models of interaction between architecture, technology, and society. The continuity of the German rationalist tradition made it possible to sustain dialogue between these models and to achieve their synthesis within a unified educational system after 1990. This historical experience remains relevant to current reforms in architectural education across Europe, which seek to establish a balance between artistic autonomy and engineering rationality.

⁵⁶ ASAP – Akkreditierungsverbund für Studiengänge der Architektur und Planung (Hrsg.): *Fachliche Kriterien für die Akkreditierung von Studiengängen der Architektur*. 6, überarbeitete Auflage. Berlin: ASAP, 2018, (§3.2-3.3), pp. 5-6; <https://www.asap-akkreditierung.de/de/ueber-asap/einbindung-des-asap/vorgeschichte>